

Radio Access Network Behavior in Urban Environment

Panagiotis Matzoros

OTE Academy S.A.

Athens, Greece

pmatzoros@oteacademy.gr

Christos Tsirakis

OTE Academy S.A.

Athens, Greece

ctsirakis@oteacademy.gr

George Agapiou

OTE S.A.

Athens, Greece

gagapiou@oteresearch.gr

Abstract— The exponential grow of data traffic, sets stringent requirements for future generation networks. The study of the existing networks allows to understand important factors for the design of the future networks. Moreover, the LTE network is going to be part of the next generation infrastructure until new infrastructures have covered all areas. This paper studies the LTE network of an entire city in terms of users' behavior and throughput. Based on the measurements in a real network can estimate the trend of users' activity in one day (24 hours) and the peak number in terms of throughput. Finally, from the measurements the required capacity is calculated for a particular city and compare today's needs with the needs at the future networks.

Keywords— CDF; LTE; capacity; future networks; multiRAT; 5G.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is well known that mobile data traffic is growing in an exponential way over the years. Traffic forecasts predict that from 11 exabytes that we use today, we will achieve 49 exabytes per month by 2021 [1]. Moreover, the tremendous increase of the devices, which require access to the network at the same time, overload the network during the day. Although today's LTE network is still improving the offering throughput and capacity, at certain times of the day can poorly undertake the vast requirements in throughput consideration from the end users and therefore it cannot meet the heavy user demands from the User Equipments (UEs). On the other hand, according to many surveys [2], the LTE infrastructure will be part of the 5G networks and the multi-Radio Access Technologies that will operate under a common controller plane in the Radio Access Network (RAN).

Our work in this paper focuses at measurements that were taken from an area that uses 4G and 4G+ LTE networks. We took measurements from the RAN and analyzed them thoroughly. In this way, we can better understand the network behavior and design it in a way to accommodate its needs according to the performance that should be achieved at the future mobile networks, the 5G networks.

II. MEASUREMENTS

The measurements have been taken from the LTE access network in an urban environment. In order to have a complete view and clear behavior of a network, the selected area was the larger region of Heraklion city in Crete island in Greece and the network is one of the biggest operators in Greece, COSMOTE S.A.

A. LTE network in Heraklion

Firstly, we have to set the city's characteristics, Heraklion is a city with area 110 km² and population 150000. The LTE access network is composed by 32 Base Stations and 150 cells in different bands and bandwidths. In Greece COSMOTE has three bands:

- 1800 MHz with 20MHz bandwidth, can offer throughput up to 150Mbps
- 2600 MHz with 20MHz bandwidth, can offer throughput up to 150Mbps
- 800 MHz with 10MHz bandwidth, can offer throughput up to 75Mbps

In most of the cases COSMOTE is establishing carrier aggregation in order to achieve higher throughput, coverage and performance.

B. Measurements methodology

The measurements have been taken from 32 Base stations, which they create 150 cells. We took traces for 24 hours during a weekday and the traces are every 15 min. The measurements that we took are:

- Data rate volume for downlink and uplink,
- Average throughput per user for downlink and uplink,
- Maximum throughput per user for downlink and uplink,
- Average users per Base Station,
- Maximum users per Base Station,

III. ANALYSIS, MODELING AND RESULTS

A. Users behavior

For the users behavior we split the analysis in two main parts. In the first part we want to see how many users, in average, have been connected to the whole LTE network during a day and the maximum amount of users that are possible to be connected in one day. From the traces we depicted that the average UEs that are connected to the LTE network per day is 70936, which means 47.2% of the total population in Heraklion and the maximum number that has been achieved was 97714 which is the 65.1% of the total population. In the second part we want to see the average and the maximum number of the active users in a Base Station distributed in 24 hours (one day). For this we focus in only two Base Stations because according to the traces the user equipments follow the same trend across all the cells.

Figure 1. The average and max users per day in BS (up to 375 Mbps throughput)

Figure 2. The average and max users per day in BS (up to 225Mbps throughput)

The above figures illustrate the activity of the UEs in two different Base Stations. The first (a) has 9 cells and has 3x3 carrier aggregation and the second (b) has 6cells and has 2x2

carrier aggregation. From the figure we can see that during the working hours the amount of active users (both in average and maximum) are higher. In addition, in both cases the amount of the active users can change but the trend remains similar which allows the operator to have a quite safe prediction of the activity in the network at least during the weekdays.

B. Throughput according active UEs

One of the most important factors for present and future networks is the throughput metric, which is important from both the operators and user perspective. From the operator's perspective because we need to deliver the services in the best quality and from user perspective because we need to offer end user quality of experience any time anywhere. The throughput analysis was at the same Base Station and cells that have been presented in the previous sub-section (A). The first Base station (BS₃₇₅) is a 3x3 carrier aggregation that can offer up to 375Mbps throughput. According to the measurements at 05:30 is the lowest activity of UEs (42 is the maximum of active UEs and 29 is the average of active UEs) and at 12:45 has the highest activity of UEs (282 maximum active UEs and 237 average active UEs). The second Base Station (BS₂₂₅) is a 2x2 carrier aggregation and can offer up to 225Mbps. According to the traces, at 04:00 is the lowest activity of UEs (49 is the maximum of active UEs and 32 is the average of the active UEs). The highest activity is observed at 18:15 (146 and 115 is the maximum and average of UEs respectively).

The figure below represents the throughput behavior of the first Base Station (up to 375Mbps) and with blue and red line is the CDF of the average and maximum throughput per user at the time of the lowest activity and with yellow and purple the CDF of the average and maximum throughput per user at the time of the highest activity. In it important to mention that during the high activity the Base Station reaches an extreme peak of throughput in order to achieve the high demand.

Figure 3. CDF of the average and maximum throughput per user at 05:30 and 12:45 (BS₃₇₅)

For the second Base Station (up to 225Mbps) the figure below shows the CDF of the throughput during the lowest and

highest activity. The blue and red line present the average and maximum throughput at the lowest activity and the yellow and purple lines depict the throughput during the highest activity. It is important to be mentioned here that the average throughput at 18:15 is less the maximum throughput at 04:00.

Figure 4. CDF of the average and maximum throughput per user at 04:00 and 18:15 (BS₂₂₅)

In both cases the Base Stations were stressed in a similar way. In addition, it is worth to be mentioned that in this measurements we did not separate the users according to their demand (service) and according to their traffic activity level. This separation can help to understand why in some cases the average throughput can be higher with less activity at certain time.

C. Required capacity

Important part of designing a network is the capacity need from the users. This factor is important not only for the present networks but also for the future networks (5G). The measurements from the access network of COSMOTE in Heraklion city allow us to determine important parameters for the calculation of the capacity need.

The formula which gives the capacity need is:

$$C_n = P_i N_i \chi \quad (1)$$

The P_i is the people per km^2 , the N_i is the UEs that are connected at the same time and χ is the data rate in Mbps. The Heraklion city has population 1364 per km^2 and according to the measurements the average of UEs that are connected at the same time is 23.2% and can achieve a peak of 32%. The results from the formula (1) give the prediction of the required capacity in the area of Heraklion city. For 23.2% is 3.9Gbps/ km^2 and for 32% is 5.5Gbps/ km^2 .

The 5G technology aims to fulfill the increasing needs for higher capacity. The key performances give the outline for the future mobile technology. From the formula (1) we are able to

calculate the required capacity needs of the next generation cellular network. As we keep the other parameters constant (P_i and N_i) we change the data rate which according to [3] is the minimum data rate in the dense urban environment. In the Fig. 5 underneath, it is illustrated the CDF of required capacity for both the existing networks and the future networks.

Figure 5. CDF of the throughput for 23.2% and 32% of activity factor for both the existing and future networks.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper we have reported the efficiency in terms of throughput of an advanced 4G, 4G+ network in an area of Greece. The results present the user traffic activity in a day and the needs of the network in terms of capacity. This need should sustain the maximum required throughput by the users. This could be verified by the peak throughput during the high activity of the base station. The current deployed 4G & 4G+ network can be the base for the future networks, (5G). Our measurements were useful in order to understand the high demands in throughput and capacity for future networks.

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